

PHYSICAL FOUNDATIONS OF NUCLEAR POWER SAFETY: EFFECT OF STEAM-PHASE SOLUBILITY ON BORIC ACID ACCUMULATION IN THE CORE OF A VVER REACTOR

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the risk of boric acid crystallization in the core of a VVER reactor under prolonged beyond-design-basis accident conditions. Unlike conservative approaches, this study uses a refined mathematical model that accounts for the removal of boric acid due to its solubility in steam. The aim is to evaluate the impact of this mechanism on the final concentration of boric acid and to assess the effectiveness of a design solution involving the reduction of initial boron concentration in Stage 3 hydroaccumulators (HA-3). The results indicate that considering steam-phase solubility significantly reduces the crystallization risk; however, additional measures are still required for complete elimination of the hazard.

Key words: VVER, NPP safety, beyond-design-basis accident, boric acid, crystallization, passive systems, steam-phase solubility, mathematical modeling.

Introduction

Ensuring the safety of VVER-based nuclear power plants (NPPs) during severe beyond-design-basis accidents is one of the key tasks of modern nuclear power engineering. Scenarios involving loss of coolant and long-term cooling of the reactor core using passive systems require detailed analysis of mass transfer processes.

One of the major hazards in such scenarios is the accumulation and subsequent crystallization of boric acid injected into the reactor to ensure cooling and subcriticality. The formation of solid deposits can block the flow areas of fuel assemblies and disrupt core cooling. Previous studies have often applied conservative approaches that do not account for boron removal via steam. This study aims to provide a more realistic assessment of the process by considering boric acid solubility in the steam phase.

Literature Review

The operation of VVER passive safety systems and the problem of boron accumulation are well covered in the scientific literature [Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.]. The necessary physical and chemical properties of boric acid solutions for the analysis are provided in other sources. Key to this study are works focused on boric acid removal via steam.

Figure 1. Flow scheme of boric acid during accidents involving leakage due to breach of the primary circuit integrity in VVER reactors [Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.]

Experimental studies on boric acid solubility in saturated water vapor were conducted by M.A. Styrikovich et al. [Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.] and A.V. Pityk et al. [Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.]. These studies established the distribution coefficient between liquid and vapor phases, providing the basis for a more accurate model. Reference [Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.] suggests that at near-atmospheric pressure, the distribution coefficient (k) can be approximated as 0.0014, enabling quantitative assessment of the boric acid mass removed with steam.

Materials and Methods

A mathematical modeling approach based on material balance equations was used to assess boric acid accumulation. Calculations were carried out for a 72-hour accident scenario at a VVER-TOI reactor. Unlike the conservative model that assumes zero boron removal via steam, this study uses a refined mass balance equation for boric acid in the reactor core:

$$M_f = M_{core} + M_{in} - M_{steam}, \quad (1)$$

where: M_{in} – mass of solution entering from hydroaccumulators, kg;
 M_{steam} – mass of steam generated due to residual heat, kg; M_{core} – current mass of the fluid in the core, kg.

Using the relationship between boric acid concentration in water and steam:

$$C_{steam} = C_f \cdot k. \quad (2)$$

The residual heat is assumed to be used for coolant evaporation inside the reactor core [3].

The condensation capacity of steam generators (equal to the heat exchangers of the passive heat removal system – SPOT) was based on large-scale experiments conducted at JSC “SSC RF – FEI”:

$$N_{SPOT} = \begin{cases} 144,8 - 5,885 \cdot 10^{-4}t + 3,499 \cdot 10^{-9}t^2, & \text{при } t \leq 86400 \\ -131,25 + \frac{7,619 \cdot 10^4}{\sqrt{t}}, & t > 86440' \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Where: t – time since the accident occurred.

Calculations were performed numerically with a small-time step. The resulting concentration values were compared with the solubility limit (≈ 415 g/kg) to determine the onset of crystallization and mass of precipitate.

Analysis and Results

The analysis was initially performed at a boric acid concentration of 16 g/kg, with subsequent simulations conducted for a range of concentrations decreasing from 12 down to 1 g/kg.

Figure 2. The accumulation of boric acid in the reactor core in different concentrations of HA-3

The results showed that the conservative model gave a final concentration of 1089 g/kg, while the refined model predicted approximately 974 g/kg. This confirms that vapor solubility is an important risk reduction factor; however, crystallization remains a major problem.

Conclusions and Recommendations

1. Accounting for boric acid solubility in steam allows for a more realistic and less conservative assessment of boron accumulation in the VVER core. While crystallization risk is reduced using standard design concentrations, it is not entirely eliminated.

2. Reducing the initial concentration of boric acid in Stage 3 hydroaccumulators (HA-3) to 1–2 g/kg proves to be an effective design measure to prevent crystallization, even within the refined model.

3. To improve prediction accuracy, additional experimental research is needed to verify the distribution coefficient under conditions close to those of a severe accident. The combined effect of steam-phase solubility and droplet entrainment should also be investigated.

References:

1. Kalyakin S.G., Remizov O.V., Morozov A.V., Yuryev Yu.S., Klimanova Yu.V. Justification of the design functions of the passive flooding system GE-2 for the

advanced VVER NPP design. Izvestiya vuzov. Yadernaya energetika. 2003. No. 2. Pp. 94–101.

2. Styrikovich M.A., Tshvirashvili D.G., Nebieridze D.P. Investigations of the solubility of boric acid in saturated water vapor. Doklady AN SSSR. 1960, v. 134, no. 3, pp. 615–617.

3. Pityk A.V., Morozov A.V., Shlepkin A.S., Sakhifgareev A.R. Experimental study of boric acid solubility in boiling steam at atmospheric pressure. Izvestiya vysshikh uchebnykh zavedeniy. Yadernaya energetika. 2019. No. 1. Pp. 30–40.

